

Electrochemical and Photoelectrochemical Behaviour of thermally prepared WO₃ Electrodes

SITANSU SEKHAR BHATTACHARYYA, ANSUMAN ROY** and S. ADITYA*

Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

Electrochemical and photoelectrochemical properties were studied with WO₃ electrodes, prepared by thermal oxidation of W foil at varied temperatures. Cyclic voltammograms show high dark currents in different pHs and in Ce⁴⁺, Ce³⁺, Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺, K₄Fe(CN)₆, methyl viologen etc. solutions. Characteristic cathodic hump was observed with each electrode under illumination or in dark. These have been attributed to the charge exchange between surface states of semiconductor electrode (S.C.) and electrolytes. The photoresponse and flatband potentials were determined using chopped light.

WO₃ electrodes have been prepared by different methods and their electrochemical and photoelectrochemical behaviour have also been studied¹⁻¹². Gissler and Memming³ investigated the current-potential characteristics of WO₃ electrodes and showed the variation of bandgap of the electrodes from 2.5 to 3.6 eV; the complex behaviour of Mott-Schottky plots of these electrodes has been ascribed to the variation donor state density. Their results indicate the extreme sensitivity of the photoelectrochemical behaviour of WO₃ electrodes using different modes of preparation. Recently Desilvestro *et al.*⁶ prepared polycrystalline WO₃ electrodes by depositing it on Ti foil. They determined the flatband potentials of these electrodes by photocurrent onset potential method and showed the reduction of Fe³⁺, Ce⁴⁺ (on rotating WO₃ electrode) in the dark as a function of potential, concentration of oxidised species and the frequency of rotation of the electrodes. Present authors have prepared WO₃ polycrystalline electrodes by thermal oxidation of W metal foils at varied temperatures and studied their electrochemical and photoelectrochemical behaviour through cyclic voltammetry (using the electrodes as stationary ones). The flatband potentials (V_{fb}) at varied pHs by the modified photocurrent onset potential method using chopped light¹³. The peaks obtained in C.V. using different redox systems like Ce⁴⁺, Ce³⁺, Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺, K₄Fe(CN)₆, I⁻, methyl viologen (MV²⁺) etc. have been assigned in dark and under illumination¹³.

Experimental

Thermal oxidation of pure tungsten foils to prepare WO₃ electrodes was done at 550–650° for a period ranging from 45 to 60 min. Ohmic contacts to copper wire were made in the rear face after scratching off the oxide layer using conducting silver paste (Dupont conductor composition 4922). The rear face and the side of the foil were

encased with teflon sheet using epoxy resin. Then it was mounted on a glass tubing through which the copper wire was taken out as terminal, keeping an exposed area (1×1 cm²) on the front surface. The electrodes were then used without etching or any other surface treatment.

The electrochemical experiments were carried out in a double-walled Corning glass cell. Water was circulated through the outer jacket to offset any ir absorption by the solution. The three-electrode cell consists of the S.C. electrode as the test electrode and a Pt foil (1.5×1.5 cm²) as the counter electrode.

Cyclic voltammetry experiments were carried out with the equipment described earlier¹³. Medium pressure mercury lamp (Hanovia), without any filter, was used to irradiate the S.C./electrolyte interface, keeping the S.C. surface perpendicular to the light path. However, on passing through the glass wall of the cell, the low uv emissions are cut out.

Na₂SO₄ (0.1 M) was used as background electrolyte for all the solutions used for cyclic voltammetry (C.V.) and pHs of the solutions were varied either by using H₂SO₄ or NaOH.

Photoresponse measurement: Photoresponse was measured for S.C./electrolyte systems with steady light as well as chopped light source as described in our earlier papers¹³.

Reagent grade chemicals were used as such. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and deoxygenated for at least 0.5 h with N₂ as and when required. pHs of the solution were recorded in a Elico LI 120 digital pH meter.

Results and Discussion

WO₃ electrodes were prepared under different conditions and designated as follows: Type-I, W foil heated at 650° for 1h, colour of the electrode

**Present address: R. & D. Centre, Chloride Industries Limited, Calcutta 700 059.

TABLE 1—FLATBAND POTENTIAL, CATHODIC/ANODIC PEAKS FOR TYPE-I WO₃ ELECTRODE

Electrolyte	pH	V _{r.b.} (V vs SCE)	Cathodic hump under illumination (V vs SCE)	Other peaks dark (V vs SCE)
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.1 M) + H ₂ SO ₄ } }	0.55	+0.47	+0.55	
	2.66	+0.30	+0.38	
	5.40	+0.20	+0.33	
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.1 M)	6.60	+0.18	+0.35	
Ce ⁴⁺ (0.05 M)	0.6	—	—	Small cathodic peak at 0.55 and large peak at 0.35
Ce ⁴⁺ (0.0005 M) + Ce ³⁺ (0.0025 M)	0.55	+0.4	+0.57	
Fe ²⁺ (0.1 M)	0.17	—	—	Cathodic peak at 0.35 and anodic at 0.55
MV ²⁺ (2 × 10 ⁻³ M)	3.0	+0.16	+0.40	Anodic hump at 0.4
KI (0.2 M)	6.6	+0.08	+0.30	
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ (0.1 M)	8.6	—	—	Cathodic at -0.05 and anodic at +0.30

TABLE 2—FLATBAND POTENTIAL, CATHODIC/ANODIC PEAKS FOR TYPE-II WO₃ ELECTRODE

Electrolyte	pH	V _{r.b.} (V vs SCE)	Cathodic peaks under illumination (V vs SCE)	Peaks in dark (V vs SCE)
Na ₂ SO ₄ + H ₂ SO ₄	1.8	+0.25	+0.55	
Na ₂ SO ₄ + H ₂ SO ₄	2.8	+0.21	+0.40	
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.1 M)	6.6	+0.11	+0.30	
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ (0.1 M)	8.6	+0.12	+0.15	
Ce ³⁺ (0.025 M)	0.6	+0.47	—	
KI (0.1 M)	6.6	+0.12	—	
Fe ²⁺ (0.1 M)	0.6	—	—	Photoresponse at least upto 0.55 for Fe ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ solution and cathodic peak at 0.4 and high reductive current for Fe ²⁺ solution beyond 0.5
Fe ³⁺ (0.1 M)	0.6	—	—	
Ce ⁴⁺ (0.1 M)	0.6	—	—	Cathodic peak at 0.15 and -0.1, anodic hump 0.75 and 0.35
Ce ⁴⁺ (0.1 M)	0.6	—	—	Cathodic peak at 0.15

TABLE 3—FLATBAND POTENTIAL, CATHODIC/ANODIC PEAKS FOR TYPE-III WO₃ ELECTRODE

Electrolyte	pH	V _{r.b.} (V vs SCE)	Cathodic hump under illumination (V vs SCE)	Peaks in dark (V vs SCE)
H ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₄	0.6	+0.04	+0.55	
H ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₄	2.8	+0.14	+0.30	
H ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₄	1.8	+0.21	+0.45	
Na ₂ SO ₄ (0.1 M)	6.6	+0.04	+0.35, -0.05	
Ce ³⁺ (0.1 M)	0.6	+0.35	+0.6 observed in dark, enhanced under illumination	Anodic peaks at 0.9 and 0.6

TABLE 4—FLATBAND POTENTIALS, CATHODIC/ANODIC PEAKS FOR TYPE-IV WO₃ ELECTRODES

Electrolyte	pH	V _{r.b.} (V vs SCE)	Cathodic hump under illumination (V vs SCE)	Peaks in dark (V vs SCE)
H ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₄	2.15	+0.15	+0.40	—
H ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₄	3.4	+0.04	+0.30	—
H ₂ SO ₄ + Na ₂ SO ₄	0.6	+0.25	+0.50	—
Ce ³⁺ (0.1 M)	0.60	+0.42	+0.55	—
Ce ⁴⁺ (0.01 M)	0.60	—	—	Cathodic hump at 0.35, increased on stirring
Ce ⁴⁺ and Ce ³⁺ (5 × 10 ⁻⁴ M)	0.60	+0.32	+0.50	—
Fe ²⁺ (0.01 M)	0.95	Photoresponse upto +0.55	—	Cathodic peak at +0.25 and anodic +0.5
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ (0.1 M)	8.6	0.3	—	Anodic peak at 0.25 and parabolic cathodic peak at 0.05

greenish yellow; Type-II, W foil heated at 550° for 1 h, colour of the electrode blue-black; Type-III, W foil heated at 625° for 1 h, colour of the electrode greenish yellow; and Type-IV, W foil thermally oxidised at 650° for 1 h but the oxidation done by pre-heating the muffle furnace at 550°, colour of the electrode greenish yellow.

The flatband potentials peaks in dark and under illumination for cyclic voltammograms with different electrolytes for Type-I WO_3 electrodes are presented in Table 1. Table 2 represents results with Type-II WO_3 electrodes. Tables 3 and 4 represent results with Type-III and -IV respectively. Type-III electrodes showed almost same electrochemical and photoelectrochemical behaviour as the Type-I electrode. The variations of flatband values were almost identical with those of Type-I electrodes. Dark currents in different solutions were also comparable. Some typical results are presented in Table 3. The $V_{f.b.}$ peaks in dark and under illumination for Type-IV electrodes in different solutions from C.V. have been tabulated in Table 4.

In general the flatband potential values of WO_3 electrodes shifted with the variation of pH of the solutions. But the variation did not follow the Nernstian behaviour, unlike the observation by Desilvestro *et al.*⁶.

Figs. 1 and 6 show that the cathodic humps formed under illumination in steady light. The hump positions shifted with pH, compatible with the variation of $V_{f.b.}$. But this hump was not direct cathodic photoresponse, as observed with

Fig. 1. C.V. of WO_3 (Type-I) using solutions of different pHs: (a) in dark and (a') under illumination; scan rate = 230 mV s^{-1} ; potential axis in V (vs SCE); for anodic photoresponse scale shifted upwards to show the oscillating photoresponse in the region of cathodic hump; current = 45 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$.

the chopped light of different frequencies (100 Hz, 2 Hz) in case of TiO_2 ¹². The cathodic hump was found to overlap with the region of anodic photoresponse. This is shown in Fig. 1. This hump could be some indirect effect of anodic process under illumination due to the existence of some surface states (S.S.). High dark current was observed for all electrodes beyond -0.3 to -0.4 V of the flatband potentials of the S.C. electrodes at a certain pH. The scanning range was controlled to eliminate the possibility of the reduction of WO_3 and hydrogen generation.

When Ce^{4+} solution (0.5 M) was taken as electrolyte to perform C.V. on the electrode (Type-I), no anodic photoresponse was observed. Two cathodic peaks were noted at 0.35 and 0.55 V in dark (Fig. 2). As a whole, the dark current was observed using Na_2SO_4 solution of the corresponding pH. The peak current at 0.35 V was large

Fig. 2. C.V. for WO_3 (Type-I) using Ce^{4+} solution (0.05 M) in dark; the effect of shaking the electrode is shown; scan rate = 230 mV s^{-1} ; potential axis in V (vs SCE).

and increased enormously on mechanical shaking of the electrode and the peak height decreased gradually and attained equilibrium when left to itself. This might be due to the concentration polarisation of the S.C. electrode. The dark current decreased with the decrease of concentration of Ce^{4+} ions (Figs. 2 and 3). With the concentration lower than 0.0005 M of Ce^{4+} ions no cathodic peaks were observed, rather the electrode showed anodic photoresponse, the C.V. pattern being exactly similar to that of the aqueous solution of same pH. No photoresponse of the electrodes in case with Ce^{4+} solutions having concentration 0.1, 0.05 and 0.005 M might be due to the high absorbance of these solutions. With dilution the cathodic peak at 0.35 V decreased proportionately. This situation is similar to those for electrodes Type-III and -IV. But in case of Type-II, the peak positions shifted to 0.1 and

Fig. 3. C.V. of WO_3 (Type-I) using Ce^{4+} solution (0.005 M) in dark; the effect of shaking the electrode is shown; scan rate = 230 mV s^{-1} ; potential axis in V (vs SOE).

-0.1 V, the larger peak being at 0.1 V. The peak at -0.1 V with 0.05 M Ce^{4+} solution showed the stirring effect as observed in case of other electrodes. The peak height (at equilibrium) decreased with dilution as observed in case of other electrodes.

In case of Ce^{3+} containing solution (0.05 M), the cathodic hump (Type-I) was higher in magnitude than those observed with the aqueous solution of same pH (Fig. 4; cf. Fig. 1). The larger cathodic hump under illumination in presence of Ce^{3+} ions at 0.6 V, may be attributed to some specific role of

Fig. 4. C.V. of WO_3 (Type-I) using Ce^{3+} solution (0.05 M): (a) in dark and (b) under illumination; potential axis in V (vs SOE); scan rate = 230 mV s^{-1} .

Ce^{3+} ions but the exact mechanism is not very clear, since only the energy levels could not explain the behaviour (E^0 of $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+} = 1.37 \text{ V}$ and the surface state energy level = 0.6 V vs SCE). Type-II and -IV electrodes showed similar behaviour with Ce^{3+} solution. In case of Type-II electrodes, however, the cathodic hump did not increase, though the dark current as a whole was higher than that using Na_2SO_4 solution of corresponding pH.

Cyclic voltammogram with Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} redox systems were interesting. The dark current as a whole was fairly high (Fig. 5). Sharp anodic and cathodic peaks were observed at 0.5 and 0.35 V respectively (in case of type, Fig. 5) for Fe^{3+} system. For the system containing Fe^{2+} almost similar C.V. was observed with the anodic peak position at 0.5 V and cathodic peak at 0.25 V.

Fig. 5. C.V. of WO_3 (Type-I) using (x) Fe^{3+} solution (0.1 M) and (y) $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution (0.1 M) in dark; scan rate = 230 mV s^{-1} ; potential axis in V (vs SOE).

The peaks were proportional to the concentrations of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions in the solutions. With dilution the peak currents as well as the dark current as a whole decreased. The other electrodes (Type-II and -IV) also showed almost similar behaviour in respect of C.V. with Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} solutions. Photoresponse at least upto 0.55 V for the above two redox systems were observed. The cathodic peak at 0.4 V and higher reductive current for Fe^{3+} solution beyond 0.5 V were observed.

In case of ferrocyanide (0.1 M) solution the dark current was also high, which was comparable with the system having Fe^{2+} solution (Fig. 5). Sharp cathodic peak was observed at 0 V and the corresponding anodic peak at 0.3 V for S.C. electrode Type-I, and in case of Type-IV the peak positions were at 0.05 and 0.25 V for cathodic and anodic ones respectively, along with high dark current. But for Type-II anodic hump was only observed at 0.5 V using $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution and much lower current was observed. The E_{p_a} and E_{p_c} values of Fe^{2+} system (in general for all types of electrodes) were 0.53 and 0.29 V (vs SCE) respectively, which corresponded the redox potential of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ system (0.43 V vs SCE). Similarly the anodic and cathodic peaks for all types of WO_3 electrodes using ferrocyanide solutions corresponded with the redox potential of ferrocyanide system.

The cathodic peaks under illumination may be attributed to the fact that the hole, generated under illumination, was quenched by the surface states in WO_3 S.C. electrodes below the C.B. (conduction

Fig. 6. C.V. of WO_3 (Type-II) in dark and under illumination with chopped light (2 Hz), position of hump under illumination with steady light also shown: (a) pH=2.85; (b) pH=1.8 (for solutions a, b); scan rate=230 mV s^{-1} ; potential axis in V (vs SCE); for anodic photoresponse scale shifted upwards.

band) and that the charge transfer through this occurred resulting in the cathodic hump under illumination while the potential was swept from anodic to cathodic direction. In acidic medium (pH=0.6) the hump was at around 0.5–0.55 V and shifted towards less negative potential with the increase of pH of the solution. So the energy level of the S.S. may be assigned at that level (0.55 V) at pH 0.6, which was independent of pH.

In case of different redox systems sharp anodic and cathodic peaks were observed in many cases; the dark currents were unusually high in respect of S.C. electrodes. It may be speculated that redox species like Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Ce^{4+} , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ etc. transferred charges to the surface states or C.B. efficiently, which showed up as the large dark currents and peaks. However, this caused the change in density of charge of the surface of the S.C.s which in turn caused the potential drop in the Helmholtz double layer. As a consequence the cathodic and anodic peaks at different potentials were observed with different redox species, depending upon the extent of charge transfer of the redox species with the electrode. The above

observation supported by the fact that flatband potential obtained with the redox species differed from what had been obtained in aqueous solution at the corresponding pHs. This is indicative of the partial Fermi level pinning of the electrode with the above redox species. The same conclusion has been arrived at by Desilvestro *et al.*⁹

For Type-II S.C. electrode as such the photoresponse and dark currents in C.V.s were smaller than those of the other electrodes. Consequently the cathodic humps were also smaller. Moreover, the electrochemical and photoelectrochemical behaviour and colour of this electrode were significantly different from those of the other electrodes. It may be due to the incomplete formation of WO_3 layer on W foil.

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